

ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS BASED ON INDIVIDUAL APPROACH

¹Khimmataliev Dustnazar Omonovich, ²Omonova Mukhlisa Dustnazar qizi

¹Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (Dsc), Professor, Chirchik State Pedagogical University

²Independent researcher, Chirchik State Pedagogical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8171848>

Abstract. *The main goal of modern pedagogical technologies is to eliminate the conflict between the average approach to all students and their individuality. The article describes new approaches in the educational system and the possibilities of organizing independent activities of students based on an individual approach with the help of electronic teaching-methodical complexes.*

Keywords: *quality, environment, material and technical base, education, science, production, integration, state, society, knowledge, skills.*

As a result of fundamental reforms aimed at introducing an effective education system in our country, the organizational and pedagogical conditions and informational and methodical opportunities for organizing independent activities of students are being expanded. In particular, in the Strategy of Actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "further improvement of the continuing education system, increasing the possibilities of quality education services, continuing the policy of training highly qualified personnel in accordance with the modern needs of the labor market" is defined as a priority task [1].

From this point of view, it is urgent to improve the actual methodology of organizing students' independent activities based on the individual approach and modern approaches, as well as to develop the mechanisms of objective evaluation of the learning results.

All modern pedagogical technologies assume the recognition of the student's individuality, which is largely determined by the direction of his development. By using modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process, the following can be achieved:

- increase in the level of motivation for education;
- it is easy for the child to learn, because the tasks are structured according to his level of knowledge;
- increasing the level of "self-concept": the strong are confirmed by their abilities, the weak have the opportunity to succeed in education, get rid of the inferiority complex;
- the teacher will have the opportunity to help the weak and pay attention to the strong;
- there will be no need to lower the general level of education;
- there will be an opportunity to work more effectively with difficult learning students who cannot adapt well to their standards;
- the level of students' activity in the lesson, as well as directly in science, increases [2].

The main goal of modern pedagogical technologies is to eliminate and mitigate the conflict between the average approach to all students and their individuality. The educational system is a social institution of society, and in many ways reflects the level of development of this society and the demands placed on it.

In recent years, there have been significant changes in science and technology, economy and politics, demographic and social structures in our country and abroad. According to the

traditional practice of reform, certain changes have taken place in the field of education, mainly aimed at improving and modernizing the educational process. The education system has undergone significant reforms related to changes in the mindset of the individual, the labor market and the demand for educational services. Reconstruction of the socio-political system requires immediate organizational and structural changes, revision of the social order, ideological and strategic guidelines [2]

The problems of organizing independent education in the continuing education system were studied in the research works of N.A. Muslimov, Z. Nishonova, T.R. Niyazmetova and others [4, 5, 6]. The organization of students' independent activities has many solutions in the practice of the higher education system, but there are no scientifically based conclusions in this area. Also, the methods, forms, tools and tasks of organizing independent activities have not been sufficiently researched. In addition, scientifically based methods, ways, and forms of organization in this field are not scientifically based, and the developed studies are not enough.

In a world of rapid change and increased flow of information, basic science knowledge is a necessary but insufficient educational goal. Students should not only master the set of knowledge, skills and competencies that are the goal of the education system (knowledge-centered). It is very important and difficult to instill in students the ability to independently obtain information and analyze it for self-awareness and useful participation in society (competence).

New approaches of the education system in modern conditions are:

- to provide access to quality education for all layers of the population;
- improvement of the regulatory framework of the national education system based on further democratization of education management;
- respect for patriotism, tolerance, high culture, human rights and freedoms;
- priority development of the state language;
- updating the content and structure of education based on national traditions, world experience and principles of sustainable development;
- reconstruction of the vocational education and personnel training system;
- to create a three-stage integrated model of personnel training (bachelor's - master's degree - doctorate) based on the accumulated credit system of education;
- to improve the quality of training highly qualified and competitive personnel for all sectors of the economy;
- integration with the world educational space;
- creation of a national system of education quality assessment;
- formation of a single informational educational environment;
- improvement of educational-methodical and scientific provision of the educational process;
- strengthening the material and technical base of the educational system;
- integration of education, science and production;
- to create mechanisms for attracting resources from economic sectors to improve the quality of education;
- increasing the social status of pedagogues, improving the financial and staffing of the educational system, training the management personnel of the educational system;
- ensure the balance of state, society and personal interests in the multi-level continuous education system.

The educational process should be focused on:

- to acquire knowledge independently and to apply it in practice, to form the need and skill of purposeful and systematic familiarization with scientific methods of knowledge;
- development of the student as a person and subject of activity, formation of valuable life instructions;
- education of respect for national culture, formation of openness to other cultural sources;
- formation of basic concepts of market economy and quality, being able to apply them in practice;
- provision of pre-professional training at the level of general primary and secondary general education.

One of the necessary conditions for implementing the above new approaches in the educational system is the introduction of new pedagogical, informational and health-protecting educational technologies. Therefore, modern pedagogical technologies are person-oriented and help not only to successfully learn science, but also to develop a person spiritually and creatively.

Organization of students' independent activities based on an individual approach is carried out through modern interactive tools with wide methodological possibilities. They include technical means that provide educational information (computers, audio and video equipment, electronic information and educational environment of the educational organization.

In the organization of education, the use of electronic teaching-methodical complexes introduced in the electronic information educational environment, including the organization of independent activities of students, increases the effectiveness of the formation of general competencies. A set of electronic teaching-methodical complexes allows communication between teachers and students in the course of classroom and extracurricular activities.

Independent classroom work is conducted in the classroom with electronic teaching-methodical complexes under the guidance of the teacher and directly under his leadership. Independent activity is performed by the student under the instruction of the teacher, but without his direct participation [7].

I.V. Kharitonova came to the conclusion that the uncertainty in the interpretation of the concept of independent activity is that different researchers interpret it as originating from different groups of characteristics: organizational, didactic, physiological, etc. This leads to the following conclusion: independent activity is a subject of didactics, psychology, methodology, etc. [8].

All definitions given by different researchers to the concept of "independent activity" are united by the fact that independent activity is aimed at forming students' active and cognitive independence.

Based on an individual approach, in the organization of independent activity of students, independent activity is formed in the process of planning and execution of project assignments of practical professional importance (information, interdisciplinary, research) that are gradually becoming more complex, which are performed with the help of electronic teaching-methodical complexes. Using electronic teaching-methodical complexes requires the development of individual approaches to the organization of students' independent activities and the ways of its implementation. Also, in order to clarify the concept of "independent activity", the following definition can be proposed: "independent activity" is "a type of internally motivated activity of a student that is carried out outside the classroom and aimed at the formation of general and professional competencies of an interdisciplinary, integrated quality, under the guidance of a

teacher it is carried out at all stages of educational activity based on interactive interaction with students and individual approach using information communication technologies.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the strategy of actions for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan". // Collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - Т., 2017. - P.39.
2. Нургалиева Г.К. Психолого-педагогические основы системы ценностного ориентирования личности. //Дисс. Док. Пед. наук. – Алматы. 1993. – 375с.
3. Хмель Н.Д. Теоретические основы профессиональной подготовки учителя. – Алматы: Галым, 1998. – 320 с.
4. Muslimov N.A. Professional formation of future vocational education teachers. Monograph. - Т.: Science, 2004. - 128 pp.
5. Nishonova Z. Training on teaching independent thinking // Public education. - Tashkent, 2000. - No1.- P. 38-40.
6. Ниязметова Т.Р. Методика самостоятельной работы учащихся на уроках узбекской литературы в IV – VII классах: Автореф. дис. ... канд. пед. наук. – Т.:1979. - 21 с.
7. Винник, В.К. Развитие навыков создания сайта у учащихся среднего профессионального образования [Текст] / В.К. Винник, А.А. Беспалько, Н.В. Сочнева // Современные проблемы науки и образования. – 2018. – № 2.
8. Харитоновна, И.В. Самостоятельная работа по теме «Неопределенный интеграл» [Текст] / И.В. Харитоновна // Математика в школе. – 1996. – №2. – С. 34